

The Phenomenon of Migration: A Linguistic and Sociological Perspective

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ABSTRACT: The empirical research, which substantiate this analysis, is developing in two researching stages. In the first phase of the research, the context of our preoccupation is the semiotical-pragmatic approach of the terms. We are interested in analysing the terminology of the word *migrație* in the scientific, respectively the common language, having at the base of the analysis the specialty dictionaries, because the semantic evolution of the words still remains a theme, which produces especially the interest of the researcher. In the second phase of the research we intend to make a radiography of a group of re-emigrant pupils, by trying to answer the questions about the typology and about the migration network, following the socio-linguistic dimension of this phenomenon.

KEY WORDS: migration, re-migration, semantics, lexical families.

Preliminaries

The topicability of the investigated theme is determined by the fact that the structuring of the lexic is one of the controversial problems of the modern semantics, by representing one of the most complex levels of the language, with interpretation's issues, because there can be established a variety of relations between the units of the lexic. There exists multiple ways of tapping the lexic, the novelty of the research being the study of the lexic of terminology of *migrație* as a system, and not as an irregular, unorganised ensemble of units.

In Romanian linguistics, the paperworks about the structured semantics are still in early phase. The research of the lexic, as many specialists tried, by "fields" (as parts more or less organised), regarding some criteria, has been shown to be more and more fruitful.

1) The Lexical–Semantic Field of the verb *a migra*

Inherited from Latin, the lexem *a migra* possesses a semantic wealth, so it can be described "step by step" through its placement in all kinds of possible "constellations".

Semantically speaking, in Romanian, the verb *a migra* is polyvalent, the sentences can be classified depending on its semantic value, developing and creating around it a series of relations.

The generic term of the category, the intransitive verb *a migra* (DN), is a neologism which came in Romanian from French (< fr. *migrer*) and Latin (< lat. *migrare*) and was for the first time registered lexicographically in the paperwork of Laurian and Massim, *Dicționar al Limbii Române*, 1876. The definition of the term, both in the general dictionaries, and in the specialties dictionaries, is strictly scientific, the content of the definitions, regarding the semantic sphere, being limited, bounded:

1. (about populations) to move in mass from a territory to another, from a country to another one.
2. (about some animals, birds) to move in mass from a place to other, in specific periods of the year.
3. (physics; about particles) to move to a given direction under the influence of different factors, agents.
4. (referring to computer users) the switch or the cause to move from a system to another.

According to *Dicționarului explicativ al limbii române*,¹ the lexem *a migra* was formed through regressive derivation from the noun *migrație*.

The character of system of the words in a language has been proven in a convincing way by Saussure, who used, in this purpose,

the notion of "associative groups" (*constelation*). This idea can be illustrated by the word *a migra*, which is associated with: *migrare*, *migrație*, *migranți*, *migrator*, *migrațiune*.²

Another associative series places the *migrant* in the neighbourhood of *emigrant*, *imirant*, *remigrant* (the recalled ideas are heterogeneous, but they still interfere through the common note "person who (e-, i-, re-) migrate", marked through the identity of the prefix).

Generally, the specialized vocabulary is improving by following the generally valid patterns, at the level of the general lexic. The lexical family of the verb *a migra* in Romanian, is composed by: *migrant*, *migrator*, *migrare*, *semimigrator*, *intermigrație*, *non-migrație*.

Some words were formed on the field of the Romanian language, borrowed through latin pathway *migrator* (< lat. *migrator*), others are borrowed from another languages: *migrant* (DN) adj., s. m. f. „(animal, human) which/who migrate” (< fr. *migrant*), and others were formed or by the derivation process: *migrare* – the verb *a migra* + the substantival suffix *-are* („the action of migration and its result”). The noun *migrație*³ has the alternative of *migrațiune* and is synonymous with the noun *migrare*, being certificated in the year 1848 and defined as "the movement of a mass of people, tribes or (a number of people), determined by causes deriving from economical, social, political circumstances or natural; the migration”.

The adjective *migrator* is certified in the year 1872 and is considered by DN as being borrowed from (< fr. *migrateur*, lat. *migrator*). The form *migrator* was formed through derivation (internal way of improving, enriching the vocabulary) from the verb *a migra* + the adjectival suffix *-tor*, such that the term has the meaning „which/who migrates, travelling”. The adjective *migrat* v. *cimirieni* „tribe with thracian origins, who migrated in antiquity from the north of the Black Sea to Asia Minor” [Pr.: *-ri-eni*] (DEX '98) is a neologism.

Although it isn't separately registered in MDA, the noun *migrațiune* is certified at least in the year 1925 in the legislation, came in Romanian through french pathway (from fr. *migration*, lat. *migratio*, *-onis*), having two meanings: 1. migration (*migrațiunea*

păsărilor), referring to the migration of the birds. 2. migrating movement (*migrațiunea unei populații*), referring to the migration of one tribe. *Migrațiunea* is not reduced only to the movement from a space to another, but seen as a releasing of some significant changes in the individual and collective life.

It is interesting that *migrația* can be a phenomenon which could change, but also an ongoing process.

We have identified an element with unknown etymology: adj. *semimigrator*, formed from the word *migrator* + *semi* – „half”, meaning „(about fish) which migrates deep in the freshwaters, moving from puddles to rivers and viceversa, or from a river to another one” (SN)

A tracing language, which reproduces the same meaning as in the biology, is the term *intermigrație*; the lexem has its origins from the english *migration* + *inter*⁻⁴, being used with the meaning of „the migration of two populations, one taking the place of the another one” (< engl. *inter-migration*) (DN).

Linguistics treats with more and more interest these complex processes, which have a large spectrum of repercussions. Studying the causes and the types of semantic changes, acad. Al. Graur claims fairly that a words' meaning is a part of the most mobile elements of a language, and the modifications at semantic order represent one of the most interesting aspects of the vocabulary's dynamics.⁵ Thus, the noun *transmigrație* (DEX), being used in another semantic sphere with the meaning „religious concept, according to which the soul from a body goes, after death, into another body”. In DN it's defined as „metempsychosis” (< fr. *transmigration*, lat. *transmigratio*).

The structure of the given lexem's field, from the perspective of the componential⁶ analysis, is the following:

- core: - [+ action], [± location], [+ membership], [+ integration], [+ direction];
- associative field : [± social effects], [± moral quality], [± origins], [± discrimination];

From the lexicographical definitions given to the verb, we can remark the occurrence of some secondary semes, of the type : [+/- Equilibrium], [+/- Identity], [+ Affect], [+/- Adaptation], [Assessment] [positive]/[negative] etc.

According to scientific documentation, we have included amongst the verb *a migra* three lexical groups/subfields: *a emigra*, *a imigra* and *a remigra*, the analysis emphasizes more characteristics and semantic preferences of the terms. If we analyse the phenomenon of migration, referring to a given population, then we can talk about three forms of migration: *imigrație* – ensemble of entries, *emigrație* – ensemble of exits and *re-migrație* – ensemble of returns, such that we can observe that any migration act is, at the same time, a migration, emigration and possibly a re-migration.

Before the detailing of the dissociation criterias, we are going to present the recurrent collocations grouped thus:

1.1. The terminology of the verb *a emigra*

The term is certified in the year 1842 by Gheorghe Asachi, being a neologism from French and Latin (< fr. *émigrer*, it., lat. *emigrare* < lat *ex* – outside, *migrare* – to migrate, to go) and has the meaning „to leave its native place, its country, to establish into another country”. In Romanian the verb *a emigra* enters into a relationship of synonymy with „a expatria”, „a pribegi” (old use), „a se înstrăina”, (old use, bookish) „a se desăra” and into a relationship of antonymy with „a se repatria”.

The lexem *emigrație* is certified in the 17th century, at Miron Costin; version: *emigrațiune*, and *emigrant*, *emigrare*, *emigrant* are certified in the first half of the 19th century (MDA).

Emigrant is a neologism from French (<fr. *émigrant*) used with substantival value „which/who emigrates; which/who is in emigration” (NEDLR), having as synonyms *expatriat*, *pribeag*.

Emigrat is a loanword from the fr. *émigré*, used with substantival and adjectival value (formed through conversion from the verb *a migra*), meaning „emigrant”. According to DS it can be synonymous with *refugiat*, *expatriat*, *exilat*, *deportat*, *fugar*, *fugit*, *pribeag*, *pribeagitor*, (old use) *surghiunit*.

The lexem *emigrare* was formed through an internal method of improving, enriching the vocabulary, namely the derivation with suffix from the verb *a emigra* + substantival suffix *-are* („the action of emigration and its result; repatriation”), having as synonymously

series (DS): *emigrație*, *expatriere*, (old use) *pribegie*, (old use, bookish) *deșțărare*, (old use) *înstrăinare*. (~ of a political combatant).

The lexical family of the term *a emigra* is completed with the noun *emigrațiune* formed through derivation from the word *emigrație* + suffix *-une*, v. *emigrație* (SN).

1.2. The terminology of the verb *a imigra*

According to MDA the verb is considered to be the most recent word in Romanian, being certified by DEX only in the year 1975. In Romanian it means „to establish into a foreign country, leaving so its homeland” (< Cf. fr. *immigrer*, lat., it. *immigrare*).

The lexical family of the verb is less numerous, compared to the others lexems, being composed of: *imigrant* (DA ms); *imigrare* (DEX); synonym *imigrație*; *imigrațiune* (DEX).

The noun *imigrare* was formed through derivation from the verb *a imigra* + suffix *-re*. The name of an action is systematically reproduced through the so-called long infinitive, becoming a noun. Its suffix is *-re*, united with the infinitive's theme (*migrare*, *emigrare*, *imigrare*, *remigrare*). These derivatives receive a concrete meaning, denoting the result of the action and even the object considered to result from action.⁷ According to DN the meaning of the term *imigrare* is „the action of immigrating and its result; establishment into a foreign country” and enters into a relationship of synonymy with the lexems *imigrare* and *imigrație*.

According to the dictionaries, the term *imigrant* is borrowed from French – *immigrant*, lat. *immigrans*, ~*ntis*, referring to „a person who immigrates (or has recently migrated)”.

1.3. The scientific terminology of the verb *a remigra*

In Romanian the documentary material gives us *remigrant* as parasynthetic derivative with the prefix *re-* + root – the verb *a migra* + adjectival suffix *-ant*.

The words of a language, like the living organisms, do not remain stationary; they are increasing and decreasing all along. „In the life of a language reigns the universal *discursus*, the ideas never rest, but always roam, receive new things and its sphere generalizes or remains bonded to a specific phenomenon, specializing itself.”⁸

The semantic extension is defined through a simple displacement of the meaning, made by the speakers on the basis of some equivalencies between two or more objects, phenomenon or actions.

The noun *re-migrant* suffered a semantic evolution too; according to dictionaries, it means:

1. *Entomology*. In aphids and another plants' louses; a female of a parthenogenetic generation with wings (sexuparae), which returns to the primary host plant, in autumn.

2. *Zoology*: In vertebrates, especially the sea turtles: an individual which migrates back to a sit in case which it grew in the previous seasons.

The actual meaning „a person or a thing who or which returns, a person who returns to the homeland, or whose citizenship was restored” is used starting with the 20th century, probably after the latin *remigrans* →”coming back” and “*remigrare* “to come back”.

The form *remigrare* is certified in the 17th century, inherited probably from the latin word stem *remigrāt-*, meaning „for moving back home, for coming back”.

1.4. The syntagmatic relations of the verb *a migra*

The linguist E. Coşeriu distinguish the relations called lexemational from onomasiological⁹ (the starting point is a signified which enter into relations with different signifieds) and semasiological¹⁰ (the starting point being a signified). Like other linguists, Eugen Coşeriu approached the problem of the classification of the lexical fields, defining two big types of structure: paradigmatic (relations *in absentia*) and syntagmatic (relations *in praesentia*). The paradigmatic structures are: primary (the notion does not need in its definition another notion)—*lexical field* and *lexical class*—and secondary (the notion does need in its definition another notion)—*modification, development* and *composition*. In the syntagmatic structures, we emphasize three types: *affinity, selection* and *envolvement*.¹¹

Because in a semantic description a ranking of meanings is imposed, we will inventorize and discuss the most frequent and

important contexts of the lexem *a migra*, used in collocations, starting from basic to increasingly distant meaning.

Migrare (migration): ~ of the workforce, ~ of pollutants in the soil, networks of ~.

Migrație (migration):

- *migrație internă/externă*¹²—referring to a national territory, we distinguish *migrația internă*, when the movement is made inside the respective country, from *migrația externă* or *internațională*¹³, when the movement is made outside the country.
- *migrații clandestine*—term used for the work called in early period migration of opportunity (because the movements of this type firstly base themselves on speculation and inventiveness in the conversion of some unfavorable or neutral circumstances into favorable situations which allow the achievement of a migration project into a place where, legally speaking, it wouldn't be possible.¹⁴
- *migrație a creierelor* refers to the fact that, from the viewpoint of the occupation and instruction, the majority of the romanian emigrants are students or they graduated an institution of higher education.
- *migrație de tip navetă*;¹⁵
- *migrație temporară/definitivă* – referring to a determined period of time, we talk about *migrația temporară*, when the person, who left for a determined period of time, remigrates and *migrația definitivă*, when the migrant does not come back anymore.
- Latent ~, phenomenon of ~, the literature of migration, ~ *etnică*, ~ *neregulamentară*, *zone de migrație naturală*, ~ *legală/ilegală*, *procese de ~*, *fluxuri de ~*.

Migranți: „migrant/immigrant workers”, traffic of migrants, the migrations of the workers, MO no. 92 from 13rd August 1975¹⁶, migrants from villages / cities – the first invests money with priority in production, in economical development, the second prefers consumption and fun.

The migrant flux, the migrant phenomenon

Migrant/-ă: migrant workforce.

Emigrare: Clandestine emigrant, definitive emigration – „total protest in relation with temporary emigration, which express a relative disproof of the departure society”.¹⁷

Emigranți:

- *emigranți de succes*;¹⁸
- *emigranți stresați* – „the emigrants with a doubtful socio-professional status or dominated by uncertainty and aspirations, this having an emotional impact over the family left home”;
- *emigranți ambivalenți* („warts and all”) encourages the occurrence of *problem children*, especially when they are teenagers, because of the tense family situation and the absence of some *certainlies*.¹⁹
- *emigranți „mioritici”*;²⁰

Imigrare: policy of immigration, the process of immigration.

2. The Implication of Migration on the Family

The second part of the study has as main objective the impact migration has on the family, intending to prove how the alternative use of two languages can influence the communication of a 10–12 years old child. To analyze this aspect, we have followed the locution of the pupils during the Romanian class and recorded the communication mistakes found in the written assessments.

We have chosen this topic, because, more or less, the phenomenon of migration affects all of us (unfortunately everyone has somebody outside the country: parents, husbands, children, nephews). After the analysis of the alarming statistics about the phenomenon of migration from our country, we have noticed the destructive effect of it on the family members. The situation of the children with parents who left the country was and is still not enough studied.

We know that, since the early years of school, the pupil begins to accumulate informations, with focusing on the communication and social integration and re-integration skills, from an inter- and transdisciplinary perspective. Thus, the communication develops itself on two axis: one of the native language and of the cognitively acquisitions obtained through it, and other of the spoken language in the adopted country, which becomes the main factor of facilitating the integration in the new social environment.

The school and the family are the two poles of education, which contribute through specific methods at teenagers' growth. Family is the first school of the child by exerting an powerful influence, which influences its moral-spiritual profile for the rest of their life. The behavior model given by the parents – which children take through imitation and learning – represents the social decisive model regarding the formation of their conception about life, and of the manner of behavior in relation with social norms and values.

The development responsibility of the child in the first stages firstly belong to the family. However families with single parents represent a particular situation. In this case, even if the endeavor of the parent are worthy of its satus, there still exist some negative aspects, which, unfortunately, can affect the child's path and development.

3. The adaptation crisis of the remigrants children

The children of the Romanians who emigrated into other countries are privileged to be integrated in an educational system, that helps them adapt, such that the newcomer has its knowledges about the language, mathematics, physics, chemistry etc. tested, in order to be able to study all the subjects with the teachers of the classes in which they are registered. These pupils benefit of special training classes, during the program, or even outside the program.

The situation of the children, who come back into the country after some time of living with their parents abroad, is difficult too. Some of them, at the age between 10 and 12 years, do not

know Romanian anymore, and cannot readjust to the Romanian communities, to the schools.

The correlation between the language and the behavior generates the interaction between social and linguistic components, and the way of using languages proves the attitude of the speaker besides the respective language (native or foreign). In the linguistic community of a country we can identify linguistic groups generated by historical factors, among which appears the phenomenon of migration.²¹

We ask ourselves whether the school can ensure a propitious context for developing the human personality, context which is based on a system with real values, helping the remigrant pupils to learn the national language, culture and values. These pupils are forced to learn to communicate in the language of the country where their parents lived, such that, linguistically speaking, the native language became, gradually, a passive tool of linguistic communication, until the native speakers have forgotten it.

What happens to these pupils who come back to the Romanian educational system which, after some researches, has a higher degree of difficulty than in the countries from which they remigrate? Unfortunately, the pupils have mostly to adapt quickly, because they don't have any additional classes for learning the language. Furthermore, they are facing different methods of teaching, some children having troubles in understanding how to approach every subject. Through remigration, the Romanian speaker is exposed to a linguistic-cultural imbalance, by his exit from his native culture, so from the native linguistic community too.

The communication in the native language represents the ability to express and interpret concepts, thoughts, feelings, facts and opinions, both in written and spoken form (listening, speaking, reading and writing), respectively to interact, linguistically speaking, adequately and creatively, in different social and cultural contexts: education and development, at work, at home and in the spare time.²²

Studying the evolution of a group of middle school pupils, I've noticed, as a Romanian teacher, that the remigrant pupils confront themselves with a linguistic barrier, which impedes them to integrate in the Romanian school environment, problem which

depends on the period of time when they were in the adoptive country. Communication in Romanian has significant differences, directly proportional to the number of the years elapsed since their departure from the homeland. I have tried to help them learn easier the language by writing some linguistic materials.

These pupils showed a variety of manifestation, referring to the phenomenon of acculturation, as the manifestation linked to the phonetic aspect, obviously influenced by the language of the adoptive country, Romanian lexical elements wrongly used, or even forgetting the grammatical structure of the native language.

Linguistic interferences, as a result of social-cultural contacts, produce diverse alterations in the language's system, which is permanently developing, reconstructing. These alterations, determined by the influence of a language on another language, consist in loaning words or in phraseological unities, adapted or not, tracing language. We consider that „two languages are in contact if they are used alternatively by the same people”.²³ The languages interference can be observed in any place where there are different languages, on the same territory or on neighboring territories.

From the interaction with these children, we've noticed that:

- many times they don't understand the communication in Romanian, and others understand it partially;
- they are using words from the other language;
- phonetically, they use erroneously diacritics, they are replacing the vowel *ă* with *a* and viceversa: „Ma (mă) numesc Mihaelă (Mihaela), Biancă (Bianca)”; they double the consonants preferring to use the geminate consonants: *r* becomes *rr*, also they are confusing the consonant *v* with *b*: „Nu știam să borbim (vorbim) bine română.”;
- they are not applying the Romanian spelling rules (they are using erroneously the hyphen in the conjugation of the verb at the subjunctive mood: „s-ă (să) învăț”);
- they are making subject-verb disagreements: „Părinții a (au) decis să plec.”;
- they forget to adapt the flexional categories of the verbs (diathesis, tense, mood, number): „Era foarte bine că înțelegem (înțelegeam) tabla înmulțirii.”;

In addition, we can say that the school is the most propitious factor for integration, having in mind that school can be the place of interaction. However, to produce a real integration there should be made some changes in the educational system, by organising some free Romanian courses, writing of bilingual materials (the involved teachers participating at these courses of learning these languages). To be able to help these children the curriculum with the school's decision to introduce an optional course of Romanian language, culture and civilization, which could be adjusted to the educational system of the country of residence, to the level of every class, to the work rate and to distribution of the content.

The actual social conjuncture (the absence of the parents who are working abroad, the necessity of counseling and careful monitoring of them) have determined the teachers to preoccupy especially about this situation.

Important is to understand that the school, cooperating with the family and the community, can assure a propitious context to the development of the pupil's personality, centered to the system of real and valid for this epoch values, flexible and easy to adapt to changes.

Conclusions

In the first stage of the research we have tried to analyze the terminology of the phenomenon of migration from an etymological and semantic perspective, the lexical field being composed of 3 lexems: *a emigra*, *a imigra*, *a remigra*. From a diachronic perspective, we have noticed that mostly the elements have been certified in paperworks since the 19th century, most of them being loan words from French and Italian.

Analyzing the structure of the word *a migra*, we have noticed that its semantic sphere can have more meanings, organised in an objective way in reality. Thus, we have observed that the verb *a migra* has not only the meaning, which is kept today, namely „to move in mass from a territory to other, from a country to other”, but it has

been enriched with the meaning „change or the cause of changing to a system to another” (referring to computer users).

The meaning of *a migra* changed through the same phenomenon of enlargement: it became comprehensive without restricting to some action. The verb *a migra* was formed from the noun *migrație*. This verb, from the special meaning of „moving in mass from a place to other, in specific periods of the year”, has received a more general meaning: „to move from a place to other, to roam or to traverse some places”. Interesting is the terminological inconsistency caused by the confusion between the long infinitive *migrare* (referring to displacement, movement on long distances of creatures) and the noun *migrație* (used to designate the internal movement of inhabitant).

The second stage of the article is dedicated to research of the family impasse induced by departing abroad. The phenomenon of migration is not reduced just to moving to a place to other, but it can be seen as a release of substantial changes in the life of the individual or of the collective. These complex processes can be treated from a linguistic perspective too.

Through remigration, the Romanian pupil is exposed to a linguistic-cultural imbalance, by leaving and coming back in the native culture, so in the native linguistic community. To facilitate the reintegration of these children in the Romanian educational system, there must be a tight collaboration between the school, pupil, family and community. Teachers can establish a communication bridge between these sides, through involving the child in extracurricular activities, which are correlated to the educational purposes. To motivate the pupils, we will use methods and complementary tools of evaluation: systematic observation of the pupils' behavior, portfolio, self-evaluation.

Integration is a long process, which base itself not only on sustained action of the remigrants children after their arrival in the country of destination, but on the receptivity, respect and support of the local population and of the authorities towards the newcomers.

Finally, to underline the role of the parent in child's life, I will quote a child of a parent who has temporarily emigrated.

A morning like many others I've lived... my parents are preparing again to go abroad. The only thought I have is that I'm not the only child who has to live these kind of moments. I sit next to my brother, who is one year older than me, and I try to hold back my tears. I didn't succeed this time either, although he wasn't braver than me. The story repeats itself every year. It almost seems normal to me to see people from my village or from my country leaving, one by one, leaving behind them a lot of tears and questions.

The idea of an agitated sea waves came into my mind. The same are the waves of my life, some taller, which toss you and knock you down, but you get up and keep going, hoping that, one day, all will be changed. Another image which overwhelms me, is of a sweater which is disintegrating into numerous threads; these threads are gathered into clews, which you put into different drawers, like I saw at my mom before she went to Spain. One day she will come back definitively, and then she will take those threads and start knitting. It will be that beloved sweater which I was wearing at school.

There are many images like this which come into my mind, and which I keep close as some priceless treasures. They help me through tough times, when I miss my parents. I like participating at school competitions, involving in sketches, the teachers even say that I am a talented actress. I participate at these activities because I know how much they would delight my parents, even though they are 3000 km away from me. Sometimes I send them recordings with me, to help them live the emotions which every parent has.

However, under the rose, I wish I would never be constrained to see my parents leaving again, as it happened this morning. I am approaching my elder brother, who is supposed now to protect me. At least, this is what mom is telling him every time.

(Vasluianu Patricia, Gânduri matinale)

NOTES

¹ *Dicționarul explicativ al limbii române, Academia Română* (București: Institutul de Lingvistică „Iorgu Iordan”, Editura Univers Enciclopedic, 1998).

² See DEX98: MIGRAȚIÚNE , migrațiuni , s . f . 1. Movement in mass of some tribes or population from a territory to other, determined by economical, social, political or natural factors; migration. 2. Movement in mass of some animals from a region to other, to breed, to search for food etc.; migration. 3. (In phrases) Oil's (or naphtha's) migration = process of moving the oil and the related gases from the ore into rocks or into a extraneous underground area. [Pr : - ți - u - . - Var.: migráție s.

³ In *Dicționarul de Sociologie*, the term *migrație* means: „The movement of a population from a region to other, especially from rural to urban areas, as well as from a society to other. In both cases, the people who migrate.”

⁴ See Alexandra Cuniță, *La formation des mots – La dérivation lexicale en français contemporain* (Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, București, 1980): The terms obtained through prefixing can be classified according to two factors: the nature of the relational element involved by the syntactic structure which it translates, and the class whom it belongs – mostly the class of the basic lexical morpheme. According to their semantic nature, the prefixes can indicate different relationships, can have some distribution. In the Romanian terminological system, the most frequent and productive prefixes are the neologistic one, acknowledged at international level. They are characteristic to the technic-scientific sphere, and they surpass its limits seldom: *a-*, *anti-*, *bi-*, *co-*, *contra-*, *extra-*, *hiper*, *intra-*, *post-* ș.a.

⁵ Al. Graur, *Schimbările de sens in Studii de lingvistică generală* (București: Editura Academiei, 1960), 212

⁶ We use componential analysis to emphasize these distinctive characteristics which help us to define the term. It was found that all lexical unities can be reduced, semantically speaking, to an ensemble of pertinent characteristics.

⁷ Ion Coteanu and A. Bidu-Vrănceanu, *Limba română contemporană. Vocabularul* (București: Editura Didactică și Pedagogică, 1975), 175.

⁸ Lazăr Șăineanu , *Încercare asupra semasiologiei limbii române. Studii istorice despre tranzițiunea sensurilor* (București: Tipografia Română, 1967), 157.

⁹ Kurt Baldinger, *Vers une Sémantique moderne* (Paris, 1984), 133: *L'onomasiologie, au contraire, part du concept qui (...) estmindépendant de la structure d'une langue donnée, pour trouver les désignations, les relations linguistiques dans une ou plusieurs langues. L'onomasiologie cherche les monèmes qui, par une de leurs significations ou sémèmes, servent à exprimer le concept en question.*

¹⁰ Ibid., p.132: *La sémasiologie part du signifié (ensemble de toutes les significations liées à un signifiant) et examine les différentes significations ou sémèmes en dégageant les sèmes ou differentiae specificaе.* (Kurt Baldinger.

¹¹ Eugen Coșeriu, *Prelegeri și conferințe* in the Yearbook of literary linguistics and history(Iași: Supliment, I, A. Lingvistică, XXXIII, 1992–1993), 88.

¹² *External migration* means solving through „violent” (extreme) ways *the conflict between the individual and society* (referring to native society).

¹³ T. Rotariu, *Dicționar de sociologie* (București: Editura Babel, 1993): international migration is, above all, an „extinction” of individuals, temporary or definitive, from a reference space.

¹⁴ Maria Cojocaru, *Efectele migrației*. Support course– *Migrația și Efectele ei în Plan Familial*, 38.

¹⁵ Vasile Miftode, *Portret al migrantului*. Suport curs – *Migrația și Efectele ei în Plan Familial*, 29.

¹⁶ International act of the Conference for security and cooperation in Europe, elaborated in Helsinki at 1st August 1975, which appeared in MO no. 92 in 13th August 1975.

¹⁷ Bogdan Voicu, *Penuria pseudo-modernă a postmodernismului românesc* (Iași: Editura Expert Projects, vol. I, 2005), 148.

¹⁸ Daniel Funeriu, *Un român deștept uluiește Europa* (București: Cotidianul *Evenimentul zilei*, 2 octombrie 2006).

¹⁹ *Ambivalence* refers to ambivalence of the attitudes, of the positions and „explanations” of different Romanian emigrants.

²⁰ The newspaper *Gândul*, 7 octombrie 2006.

²¹ Mina-Maria Rusu, *Educația sociolingvistică în contextul migrației* (Chișinău: Revista *Limba Română* nr. 7–8, 2011).

²² Mina-Maria Rusu, *Competența de comunicare – perspective de abordare* (Chișinău: Revista *Limba Română* nr. 11–12, 2009).

²³ Uriel Weinreich, *Languages in Contact*, With a preface by André Martinet, *Third Printing* (Hague–Paris–Mouton, Mouton & CO, 1964), 1.